

No playing around with robots? Ambivalent attitudes toward the use of Paro in elder care

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Funding information

Smart Homes, Older Adults, And Caregivers: Facilitating Social Acceptance and Negotiating Responsibilities [RESOURCE] project; Swiss National Science Foundation (SNF NRP-77 Digital Transformation), Grant/Award Number: 407740_187464/1

Abstract

This paper explores the ways in which health care professionals, family carers, and older persons expressed attitudes and opinions on using Paro, a social robot designed to stimulate patients with dementia. Thereafter, we critically evaluate existing prejudicial views toward Paro users to provide recommendations for its future use. Using an exploratory qualitative interview method, we recruited a total of 67 participants in Switzerland. They included 23 care professionals, 17 family carers, and 27 older persons. Data obtained were analyzed thematically. Study findings present general agreement that Paro is an appealing and beneficial social robot, but it is not a tool that everyone feels comfortable with. Because it is perceived as “child play,” it would be demeaning for competent adults to play with such things. Consequently, Paro is appropriate only for persons with dementia. These findings brought forth ethical concerns about deception, infantilization, and respecting older persons' dignity. The idea of *who* is an appropriate Paro user led to our discussions on predicting future Paro users. The meaning of using social robotics in nursing homes can be conditioned by a rigid interpretation of adulthood and playful behavior. To protect future selves when one is living with dementia from prejudices, it may be useful for older persons and their loved ones to plan their future care situations to ensure that they are treated in accordance with their delineated decisions.

KEYWORDS

dignity, elder care, future care planning, Homo Ludens, nursing homes, Paro, qualitative study, social robots

1 | INTRODUCTION

Social robots can help users to recover and rehabilitate. One well-known example of a social robot renowned for its appealing design is Paro—a seal-like robot developed by Japan's National Institute of

Advanced Industrial Science and Technology. By responding to the user's touch and sound, Paro creates a personalized interactive experience, surpassing mere toy-like interactions (Coghlan et al., 2021; Dudek et al., 2021). Nicoro (cat-like), Pleo (dinosaur-like), and Aibo (dog-like) are other animal-like robots that have been designed and

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studied (David et al., 2022). Among these robots, Paro stands out as the most popular due to its cuteness, intuitive use, and commercial availability (Baisch et al., 2017; Bemelmans et al., 2012).

Researchers have extensively examined Paro's effectiveness in supporting older patients, especially those with dementia. Over a decade ago, Bemelmans et al. (2012) conducted a review that encompassed eight studies involving Paro's utilization in nursing homes and with older persons with dementia. They found positive effects of social robots on mood, loneliness, social connections, communication, and stress. More recent reviews continue to substantiate similar positive impacts (Hung et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2022). Along the line of positive outcomes, a study noted how older persons living in institutional settings in Taiwan can form meaningful experiences with Paro (Chen et al., 2022). However, in an ethnographic study from Japan, nursing home carers were concerned about an older resident who self-isolated herself by overly engaging with Paro (Wright, 2023).

The use of social robots is expected to help address the care needs posed in light of the rising older adult population (Astell et al., 2019; Sekhon et al., 2022). Though recent reviews confirm acceptance of social robots in the elder care context (David et al., 2022; Naneva et al., 2020), the high acceptance rate might not be an indication of a positive choice by its end users. Underneath, it could also be an issue of lacking alternatives (David et al., 2022). Currently, we may lack options, but new and emerging technologies are anticipated to address the issue of generating diverse meaningful engagement for older adults living with dementia, who by no means have homogenous preferences. For example, virtual reality is foreseen to be used as an entertaining and therapeutic technology (Hayden et al., 2022). Older adults can virtually travel to various destinations around the world (Fiocco et al., 2021), and access immersive gardening therapy programs using virtual reality (Lin et al., 2020). Smart home technologies, like sensors that stimulate exercising programs and fall detection devices, are also expected to be applied to the care of older adults (Pageau, Wangmo, et al., 2024).

However, the adoption of technologies is not only based on their technical benefits alone. It depends on how various stakeholders make sense of such technologies within the broader social context, which includes social norms, values, and relationships (Chang & Šabanović, 2015; Chevallier, 2022). Empirical studies have underlined that ethical concerns may deter acceptance of such robotic technology in elder care (Ienca et al., 2018, 2021; Wangmo et al., 2019). Scholars have written about deception, dignity, and personhood concerns with the use of robots to care for older persons (Sharkey & Sharkey, 2012; Sparrow, 2016; Sparrow & Sparrow, 2006). The potential of stigma and ageism have also been raised as a real danger in newer literature (Battistuzzi et al., 2021; Coghlan et al., 2021; Felber et al., 2023; Hung et al., 2019). For example, Dudek et al. (2021) explored the opinions of 28 older adults in Germany about a dinosaur-like robot called Pleo. Their study revealed that people who used Pleo were cast in an unfavorable light, being perceived as socially isolated and lacking competence. Similarly, Vandemeulebroucke et al. (2020) carried out focus groups with older adults in Belgium and discovered that the participants

projected loneliness and diminished abilities onto potential users of social robots. More than a decade ago, Neven (2010) adverted to stereotypes associated with being a robot user: an older person, lonely, and in need of company. Differently, recent qualitative studies with older persons with dementia using Paro did not report concerns related to stigma, only positive health benefits (Hung et al., 2021; Pu et al., 2020).

The uncertainty about when stigma is associated with users of social robots emphasizes a tension between two decisional contexts: choosing beforehand (when people are healthy) and choosing amidst the complexities of a disease when ethical concerns become ripe. Consequently, there is a significant demand for a decision-making framework that aids in understanding and selecting new technologies in elder care. The use of advanced care planning as a framework to make future choices may greatly contribute to safeguarding the well-being of individuals who will be unable to make competent decisions. To address the uncertain conditions of stigmatization and establish a foundation for framework development, our study assessed existing prejudicial views toward Paro users. Therefore, the research questions that guided our data analysis were (a) how older persons, family carers, and professional care providers express their attitudes and opinions regarding the use of social robots capable of personalized interactions; and (b) what recommendations can be developed about its future use in nursing environment for older persons?

2 | METHODS

This paper is part of a larger national qualitative exploratory study that aimed to elicit the perspective of three different stakeholder groups: older persons, family carers, and professional care providers on the use of smart technologies in the care of older persons. In this paper, we evaluated the social robot, Paro, to address the research question delineated above. Other manuscripts from the larger study evaluated the acceptance of all technologies using the technology acceptance models (Felber et al., 2024) and examined the monitoring technologies within the framework of care ethics (Martani et al., 2024).

The national study was assessed by the Ethics Commission of Northwest and Central Switzerland (EKNZ). All participants received an information document before the interview date detailing the purpose, procedure, and anonymization measures. They were also made aware that they can withdraw their participation at any time and need not feel any discomfort in stating that to the interviewer. After explaining the study and receiving their written informed consent, the interview process began.

2.1 | Interview guide

The interview guide included three sections: General questions to understand the participants and their care needs (or care provision in

the case of caregivers); specific questions for each of the technologies included in the study; and concluding questions. We presented pictures of the following smart technologies: wearable sensors, ambient (visual) sensors, assistive robot (Pepper), social robot (Paro), and VR glasses. In the case of the robots, we also showed the participants a video clip from YouTube.¹ However, the Paro video was discontinued at the initial stages of data collection as the video featured older persons with dementia and older participants reacted with worry about dementia, not focusing on Paro anymore. Thereafter, we presented all remaining participants with a picture of Paro to elicit their responses. For each technology introduced, we asked a series of questions (e.g., their impressions and experiences, benefits and barriers they saw, opinions on using or not using, its impact on caregiving, and conditions of use). The final section asked them to compare the different technologies and sought their general recommendations for the use of such technologies in elder care. In the case of Paro, the questions were "Now I'll show you Paro, a pet-like robot that is often used for companion purposes: (a) What do you think of this robot? (b) How would you feel about using Paro as a 'pet'? (c) What problems/concerns/opportunities do you see with using robots in a caregiving context?"

The interview guide was originally written in English, then translated to German and French by a bilingual research team member, and back-translated by independent bilingual assistants. This process therefore enabled the research team to ascertain that the data collected in both languages by different team members were as coherent and consistent as possible. In light of the semi-structured nature of the interview process, the interviewers could adapt the question to ensure understanding. As customary in qualitative research, for each participant group, the interview guide was adapted and further improved, where needed, based on the first few interviews.

2.2 | Participant recruitment

Study participants were purposively recruited to reflect the aims of the study. Eligible interviewees must be either (a) older persons over 65 years of age receiving care at home or a nursing home or an assisted living facility; (b) family carers providing support to an older person, either a parent, grandparent, or a spouse; and (c) professionals working in nursing homes, home health care agency (Spitex), and assisted living facility. For the recruitment, we used different techniques and channels to advertise our study to prospective participants or individuals who can direct us to possible participants. We thus disseminated information about our study on social media, proactively contacted organizations serving older persons and their care providers, home care providers, nursing homes, assistive living facilities, and distributed flyers through services such as Meals-on-

Wheels. The interviewer asked study participants for suggestions to contact further persons fulfilling the study criteria.

2.3 | Data collection

Two female Swiss interviewers conducted all the interviews in the German-speaking part of the country. One interviewer (N. A. F.) was completing her PhD in biomedical ethics at the time, and the second (V. D.), was finishing her master's education in medicine. They both received training in qualitative methodology before carrying out the interviews.

A total of 67 participants were recruited. This included 27 older persons, 17 family carers, and 23 professional care providers. The older persons were on average 87.4 years old, family carers were 57.1 years old, and professional care providers were 45.2 years old. Among the total 67 participants, 15 were older female participants, 13 were female family carers, and 19 were female professionals. Older participants were living independently at home or at a nursing home or an assisted living facility. None of the older participants had dementia at the time of the interview. Family caregivers included those caring for an older person with dementia and those caring for older persons with other care needs. The professionals were nurses, nurse aids, home nursing care providers, and those working in assisted living facilities.

The interviews were completed in participant's homes or a place of their choice. The interviews were on average 96 min long (range: 46–189 min) and were completed between September 2021 and October 2022. The interviewers met the participants for the first time during the interviews and there was no prior personal relationship with any of the participants. In a few cases where the participants were short of time (e.g., care providers) and got tired (e.g., older participants), the interviews were stopped and another date to continue the discussion was arranged.

2.4 | Data analysis

Each interview was transcribed verbatim by the same two interviewers from Swiss German (dialect) into High German. For this paper, all coded segments along with the code names corresponding to Paro were extracted and transferred into an Excel sheet. The first author carried out the preliminary analysis for the paper during which the coded segments were read and reread, and codes were renamed (e.g., infantilizing, deception, real vs. not real; for persons with dementia; serves a purpose; less work than real animals). These preliminary findings were audited by the last author (E. M.). They discussed the content of each theme and its corresponding subthemes, and the connection between the themes (Figure 1) addressing the goal of this paper (Guest et al., 2012). The co-authors (V. D., N. A. F., and A. T.) read the refined findings resulting in adaptations to the content of the results as well as its interpretation.

¹For Paro: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=agia008ms84&t=71s>; for Pepper: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UMWksQz3aOo&t=3s> (shown until 1 min 14 s).

FIGURE 1 Using Paro in elder care.

3 | RESULTS

We begin our results with the thematic map representing the connection between the themes and subthemes (Figure 1) in this section. Exemplifying quotes appear in italics and within quotation marks. They were translated into English from German and edited to ensure readability. Each quote is followed by information on the participant group (OP = older person, FC = family carer, PC = professional care provider; H = home, N = Nursing Home, D = dementia, R = nondementia). For example, OPH means older participant living at home; PCN denotes professional caregiver working in nursing home, FCD stands for family carer of older person with dementia, and FCR is a family caregiver for an older person.

3.1 | Paro is not everyone's cup of tea

3.1.1 | Paro's use is inappropriate: Infantilization and deception

The majority of the older participants felt that a robot such as Paro is not acceptable to be used for older persons, bringing forth the notion of infantilization. In several cases, they stated that they could not imagine using *Paro* for themselves as well because it is an object that children play with. An older participant highlighting that she would not like such a thing stated: "OPN7: *I'm just not a fan of that kind of thing. [It is] ok, for children, I can imagine that could be interesting because it does something.*" Also, older participants evaluated Paro as a strange thing that would be of no use for them (and older persons like them) due to the capacities they possess.

OPN9: "It is not a being, [its] such a strange thing, and that I can turn it on when I feel like and turn it off again when I have had enough. No, I can't imagine that [using

Paro]. If it is something to give to a child and [the child] has a little fun with it, yes, why not? But no, as an adult, no [Paro is not for me]. Not at all."

Although many older participants acknowledged that Paro looks like a small soft animal and that it is "cute," they discussed their discomfort raising fears associated with deception: "OPN8: *It might be nice, but (sighs) I'm just not into that kind of thing, I'm not into that kind of thing.*" They rejected Paro because it is a *thing*, which was presented as a living being: "OPH7: *Yes, for me it is not real enough ... Either or ... it is like ... between the chairs.*" Older participants further raised doubts about using Paro even for those with limited cognitive capacity stating that they would prefer to be treated as an adult and have human contact. In doing so, related to the ethical concepts of infantilization and deception, notions of dignity and recognition as persons were highlighted.

OPH2: "[Paro is] Not real. It is difficult to know the reality once you're that far [have dementia]. And I think it's actually a shame that you then use things like that [Paro]... I'd rather have a face-to-face conversation or somebody to talk to. So some kind of contact person ..., I think that's much more realistic than ... childish or childlike ... becoming childish. Maybe it may also happen to me, I'm aware of it. But would I still notice it [Paro] or not? But I don't think I will enjoy such stuffed animals [Paro]."

On this topic of not wanting to use Paro, a few professional participants discussed their personal preferences for real animals. They themselves would rather have living animals that could run and jump around, and not something that is fake. As professionals, they understand that Paro is generally well accepted in the health care setting but would still prefer to have something real for themselves (in the future): "PCH4: *I think, Paro is quite well received, I read about it.*

I would rather have a cat that is alive." In response to whether a participant would prefer to receive a Paro from her children, the participant clearly expressed the choice for human contact and to be alone with a real animal than a robot, *"Then I say, 'Don't you have time for me anymore?' I want my social contact ... And otherwise I'd rather stay lonely, alone, and get a real dog or cat, so no, no. For me real is, real."*

Similar to professional participants, one family carer clearly noted that the use of Paro with any older person (with or without dementia) is not acceptable because it does not respect the inherent dignity of the person. *"FCR2: ... I also found it a bit infantilizing, that such a thing was used at all [in nursing homes]. That is simply my perception."* Along the same lines, there were other family carers who felt that Paro was not something they would want in the future. One participant underlined preference for a stuffed toy rather than a robot in the future: *"FCD1: No. I might as well get an old stuffed animal out of the attic. If that were the case [i.e., to use Paro] (laughs)."*

3.1.2 | Paro for certain older persons

Paro for older persons with dementia

As evident from the theme above, the three participant groups did not feel unanimously enthusiastic about Paro. They associated Paro with older persons with dementia and felt that this group would benefit from it. This usability of Paro for and by older persons with dementia was due to their reduced capacities to comprehend that it is not a real animal. Acknowledging deception and noting that even if older persons with dementia confuse the robot with a real animal, there are still some benefits to the user justifying its deployment for this group: *"PCH6: So if using Paro does them good, then it would definitely be ok... We always have clients who have a stuffed animal or a doll or so and treat it as if it were real."*

In the previous theme, we saw that a reason for deeming Paro inapplicable for themselves was the comparison with children. But here, we see that this comparison is normalized when it comes to older persons with dementia. That is, they were seen as someone who could play with toys (like children). Often mentioned, as evident in the above quote as well, was the observation that older persons with dementia would carry a toy around with them and treat the toy as if it were real.

PCN9: "So Paro would be actually [good] ... because I suppose it does not feel pain as a robot. People who have dementia can like play [with it], or [it will be] a good occupation, a good relationship, I think. And we also have many residents who hold on to a doll all the time, or always take with them or like a, stuffed toy dog, always take it with them on the walker. So I can very much imagine that this helps [the person]."

Understanding that this association is acceptable, few participants (older persons and family carers) felt that they would be willing to use Paro if they were in the same situation. That is, one participant

discussed how Paro might be useful when the mother's cognitive capacity deteriorates, as she typically likes small animals. The reason for believing that Paro is not appropriate now is out of respect for her current capacity and the fact that she will realize that Paro is not a real animal. Therefore, all the participant groups reported that Paro cannot be used for persons who have cognitive capacity as they would recognize that it is not a real animal: *"OPH1: But what do I know, when the time comes that I cannot manage things [for myself] and, ... then I'd probably be happy for anything that gives me a nice, comfortable day. Or a good feeling."*

FCD4: "Yes, I can imagine something like that. I have observed that she [the mother] is more and more responsive to animals, so when she sees an animal somewhere, or even toddlers or babies, she now has much more of an eye for them and goes up to them and wants to pet. I don't know, maybe now it [introducing Paro] would be a bit too early. ... So I think she possibly still realizes that now ... maybe in half a year or a year [when dementia deteriorates], that would be different."

Paro for older persons living alone

In addition to seeing the value of Paro for older persons with dementia, some family carers stated that Paro could be used for older persons living alone as they would have something familiar with them. Having Paro with an older person living alone might reduce the burden of care for the caregivers. From the other two participant groups, this association of Paro use with older persons living alone was not prominent, but a few spoke about Paro being useful for those with limited physical capacities.

"FCR6: And also otherwise someone who does not have dementia but is alone, and no longer has a cat. In this case, the person is a bit sad in the evening and has something that can help out, in such cases, I would have no trouble [with using Paro] at all."

3.2 | Finding space for Paro in elder care

3.2.1 | Paro is easier to "care" for

A few participants from the three groups mentioned that a positive outcome of Paro is its potential to replace small animals as older people may have (have had) pets. Study participants agreed with this replacement due to comfort provided by animals, and because very older persons and those with dementia may not be able to care for the animals either at home or in a nursing home. Further, bringing one's own animal into the nursing home might not be possible, making Paro an alternative: *"OPN9: I think that for many people, who maybe have had a pet for a long time, and are of course, not allowed to*

take it with them [to a nursing home], it's quite clear that it [Paro] may already give a certain comfort."

"FCR5: We have also talked about whether a real cat would be something for her at home in the apartment. But what she can no longer do is clean the litter box and bend over to wash the bowl and fill it again with water and food. So all the care aspects of such a pet, they prevent her from having a real animal. And that will all be gone with a little robot, you only have the pleasant petting and purring and that you have the feeling that you're not so alone."

However, concerns were raised that use of Paro might replace human contact. One older participant feared that in light of a lack of time to listen to an older person, a nursing care provider might "give them one of these and then it's goodbye" (OPH4). A professional caregiver underlining a similar situation talked about how Paro helps with loneliness felt by older residents and allows the nursing staff to move on to other responsibilities she or he may have. A few family caregiver participants also echoed such fear.

PCN8: "... sometimes with people [residents in nursing homes], when we go out of the room, we give them something to hold, when we have to go away and they can't hold onto us anymore, that we give them either a doll or a teddy, and that's very much appreciated ... Or when you go out, that Paro stays a little bit and it's not so lonely again suddenly."

3.2.2 | Paro gives comfort and is harmless

Several older participants stated that Paro can be used for older persons because of its positive effects. They felt that Paro is warm to hold, it gives older persons a feeling of being occupied, and that they will have fun with it. Specifically, for older persons with dementia, it keeps them busy as they have something to touch and feel connected to, as well as a possible form of therapy: "OPH4: Well, if it does something good in nursing homes' dementia department, then I would use something like that. I think so. Why not? Now that's something that's going to do some good, I mean. Isn't it?"

Similarly, both caregiver groups saw the use of Paro as harmless. Few family carers described that its similarity with a toy and a small animal has the potential to bring about positive outcomes: "FCD5: It's just better than a cat actually, like a stuffed animal, that's why we tried it, she can pet it, no risk of injury." One participant further highlighted that Paro is harmless as it is not intimidating and could be discarded, when and in case an older user feels partial to it: "PCN9 ... Yes, I think that Paro, for example, I can use without any thoughts, because ... Paro doesn't really do anything in theory, it's like an animal ... they react maybe a little bit, but not so much talking or doing something."

The potential positive benefits of Paro, in this case, justified its use in elder care. This point was underlined by a participant who concluded that using Paro for older persons with dementia brings happiness, in which case, there should be no consideration surrounding infantilization. On the contrary, their happiness shall be considered as the final good.

FCR10: "Yes, I saw that show where they introduced it to persons with dementia. And I have to say, that's absolutely, I think that's absolutely great. Because I think that's what you really have to focus on, everything that is still nice and yeah ... I don't think you should question, are we taking them back to childhood or ... And if it brings joy, if you see, they have joy ... I mean, you also see it with dolls sometimes. I think that's good, yes."

Related to the "no harm" argument was (as stated previously) the general idea that older persons (with or without dementia) tend to like animals and toys and that they "happily" carry a toy with them. Paro was deemed to provide some social contact that is lacking in the nursing homes and thus could give a feeling of companionship: "PCC5: And maybe also with people who are rather a bit withdrawn and for them it could be real, like a bit of a companion." Furthermore, one participant underlined the sense of responsibility that older persons with dementia, particularly older women, feel when they "care" for Paro.

PCN4: "We have ... I still know it from dementia care, there are various dolls that—but these are not electronic, no robot, they're just dolls, they're just the size of a ... size and weight of a baby, are also very firm, not soft like a teddy bear and in the caregiving setting that was a huge success, especially to calm women, when they had such a doll, they were simply really caring about it and are back in their task also as a mother ... but that is really with persons with severe dementia. I'm really a proponent of tools like that."

3.3 | Past preferences predict future Paro users?

Older participants justified Paro's use with their general observations of past preferences of animals and/or toys. For instance, a few said that they never had an animal their whole life, hence would be just fine without Paro. Others felt that as some older persons have had animals, they may prefer Paro as a substitute. Likewise, more than half of the family carers, on discussing Paro's usability, expressed that the use and nonuse of Paro in caregiving situations would depend on their older parent's prior preferences. In doing so, the family carers created a category of possible future users. For example, there were family carers who believed that their parents would not like animal-like robots based on their parents' nonpreference of animals in the

past: "FCR10: You also have to know, for example, that dad never wanted a dog. Dad is not [someone who wants] a pet." Alternatively, the same participant reported liking toys and animals, and would be happy with Paro even when he or she is not aware that it is not a real animal: "FCR10: I'm completely crazy for them [animals and stuffed animals], well, I mean, if I were to receive a Paro someday, I probably wouldn't know anymore [would have dementia then], but I would probably take it (laughs)."

Additionally, few family carers felt that when older parents have dementia, it would be acceptable to use Paro due to their prior preference for animals. Conversely, other family carers revealed that because of this prior preference for animals, they may decide against using Paro since it is not a real animal: "FCR8: She always enjoyed it when I take our dog with me. She thinks that's great. But this [Paro] she would find [as something that is] soul- and heartless."

FCR2: "My neighbor [understands] nothing anymore. She had a little dog, a Chihuahua that she loved. She had him for hours on her lap. So I can imagine that this [Paro] can be a substitute. But it [the cognitive limitation] really has to be quite advanced, so with my parents it wouldn't be an option now."

4 | DISCUSSION

Our study gathered opinions on Paro from its future end-users (older persons) and indirect users (family carers and care professionals) who may use such technology to find some reprieve from their caregiving roles. Other studies, capturing data on Paro or other social robots, focus on one participant group, for example, older persons or care providers (Birks et al., 2016; Chang & Šabanović, 2015; Ienca et al., 2021; Moyle et al., 2018, 2019), and underscore its positive impacts (Chen et al., 2022; Fracasso et al., 2022; Hung et al., 2019; Moyle et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2022). Our findings, in addition to the ethical concerns of infantilization, deception, and respect for dignity (Sharkey & Sharkey, 2012; Sparrow, 2016; Sparrow & Sparrow, 2006), shed much-needed light on prejudice toward robot users (Dudek et al., 2021; Vandemeulebroucke et al., 2020) and the complex considerations surrounding the present and future deployment of robots as possible companions. In the following sections, we relate our results to these concerns and propose a framework of care planning for future selves.

4.1 | Being busy with Paro

From our research, Paro brings apparent benefits in caring particularly for older persons with dementia. The vast body of literature repeatedly highlighted the psychological, quality of life, and companionship benefits for older persons with dementia with the use of animal-like social robots (Abbott et al., 2019; Birks et al., 2016;

Kang et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2022). Participants also reported benefits, irrespective of whether they felt Paro was appropriate to use or not, and for whom it should be used. Based on their direct professional experience with older persons, in the case of nursing care providers or their observations as older persons and family carers, these assessments spoke to Paro's calming effects. For some older persons, Paro enables its users to reconstruct their days around the sense of "being busy" by taking care of an "animal" or a "baby." Compared with pets, who are capable of complex interaction but can be difficult for older persons to manage, Paro as a social robot offers a practical interactive companionship through touch and sound that cannot be reproduced by mere toys (Coghlan et al., 2021; Dudek et al., 2021).

Nevertheless, participants repeatedly compared Paro to stuffed toys and real animals, raising the question of whether Paro is categorically better than these alternatives. In another qualitative study, a nursing administrator rejected the use of Paro because for the same price, many sessions with animals are possible (Wangmo et al., 2019). Golant (2017) underlined factors that may help determine the adoption of smart technology versus traditional solutions. So, we have to make trade-offs between the degree of complex companionship and practical feasibility when deciding upon available options. Furthermore, we have to be aware of the risk that older persons with dementia may overly attribute meaning to social care robots (Chen et al., 2022), and perceive them as subjects they should care for, rather than focusing on self-care (Wright, 2023).

4.2 | Finding happiness in unreal objects

An intriguing reason for deeming Paro acceptable for older persons with dementia was their diminished capacity to discern the difference between real and fake. They may confuse Paro with a real animal and find companionship (Hung et al., 2021; Pu et al., 2020). The view that older persons with dementia "would not know" justified the use of Paro according to our study results. Such things (animal-like robots) are considered beneficial and therapeutic because older individuals often carry around a toy and seem happy about it. Also, a few family caregivers noted that they themselves would find it reasonable to use Paro when they have dementia since it is likely to enhance their happiness. Similarly, to ensure happiness, others would use Paro for their older parents when they have dementia, but not at present, as their parents are competent and would not appreciate the gesture.

Some scholars have argued that deception is wrong (Sharkey & Sharkey, 2012; Sparrow, 2016; Sparrow & Sparrow, 2006). The idea of older persons with dementia finding happiness in unreal objects, and participants noting that they would also value their happiness (at the time when they have dementia) more than deception concerns, raises the important issue of respecting the reality experienced. Such reality can take different forms and make sense to the experiencing subject. Older persons with dementia usually retain their active ability to value long after other self-governing capacities are gone (Jaworska, 1999). For this reason, we should try to understand that

the reality of older persons with dementia is different in several aspects from competent adults and, consequently, that deception is more instrumental in eliminating harm and fulfilling personal values in the former than in the latter (Tuckett, 2012).

4.3 | The dignity of *Homo Ludens*

While individuals with dementia may embrace Paro as a valuable companion, many participants from the three groups found Paro unsuitable for themselves as older persons or in anticipation of their own aging. The rationale for rejecting Paro was that it is like a toy, suitable for children and not for competent adults (like themselves), despite its calming effects. They believed that playing with toys was beneath the dignity of mature individuals and that associating older adults with Paro would be demeaning and patronizing. Embedded in this toy argument is the ethical concern of disrespecting the dignity of older persons by using such fake objects (Coghlan et al., 2021; Ienca et al., 2021; Sharkey & Sharkey, 2012; Sparrow, 2016; Wangmo et al., 2019). It is as if a competent adult has to interact with real people, whereas children are allowed to play with unreal characters.

The sense of dignity related to the perceived inappropriateness of engaging with toy-like social robots warrants scrutiny. Participants seemed to have an intuitive concept of dignity based on status recognition, although in a few cases, the universal recognition of dignity. In the former understanding of dignity, to respect someone's dignity means to recognize their status and treat them in accordance with what their status requires (Rosen, 2012; Waldron, 2012). For example, respecting the dignity of a judge in the courtroom requires adherence to the established norms and protocols, which serve as a sign of reverence. Similarly, respecting the dignity of adults involves adhering to social standards that encompass various aspects, including appearance, independence, and adult competence. Acknowledging their maturity and capabilities is essential in upholding their dignity, and part of their maturity is that they know what is real and prefer to stay in contact with reality. Consequently, speaking to them as if they are children and assuming that they still believe in fantastic stories are signs of disrespect.

When introducing robotic technologies to support older persons, we have to be mindful of not infantilizing older persons. Imposing childlike roles and norms on individuals with dementia can suppress their right to self-determination. Furthermore, infantilization can lead to social discrimination. By emphasizing childlike qualities and disregarding adulthood, infantilization can contribute to biases and discrimination against older persons with dementia.

At the same time, a conception of dignity based on status recognition can become rigid and subject to unwanted influences. In certain contexts, the status of being an adult is determined by conservative beliefs, stereotypes, and misconceptions. In our case, some participants adhered to a strict definition of maturity that seems to exclude playfulness. Children play with toys, not adults (they have to be serious). Children have imaginary friends, adults are

constrained by what is real. It is possible that these participants held different views on the types of play appropriate for children and adults. However, this interpretation of the dignity of competent adults can be a vehicle for prejudices against older persons with dementia who fail to exemplify these attributes, being treated as socially inferior (Barclay, 2018; Pageau, Fiasse, et al., 2024). Maybe harsh experiences and cultural norms, that define adulthood in terms of seriousness and strict standards of enjoyment, make us forget that human beings are *Homo Ludens*. Child play and adult play form a continuum, not two distinct categories. There is a natural progression from the unstructured play of childhood to the more organized play of adulthood, but the joy of recreation can remain throughout all stages of life. As Huizinga puts it, "we have gradually become convinced that civilization is rooted in noble play and that, if it is to unfold in full dignity and style, it cannot afford to neglect the play-element" (Huizinga, 1980). Being able to laugh, to play, to enjoy recreational activities is a central human capability (Nussbaum, 1999).

4.4 | Implications on the use of social robots in elder care settings: Deciding for future selves

Previous studies with competent older adults have also reported potential stigma associated with the use of new technologies in the elder care context (Coghlan et al., 2021; Dudek et al., 2021; Felber et al., 2023; Hung et al., 2019). The negative association between Paro use and being cognitively deficient, however, calls for attention at the level of family, clinical care, institutional care, and the society. Although technology may appear neutral, it is not (Miller, 2021; Strate, 2012). The context where it is deployed may create and recreate meaning with its usage.

How can we curb prejudices existing with the use of social robots, while at the same time harness the benefits of such technologies? Our findings on future users of Paro suggest a tangible tool. We propose the framework of future care planning for technology use in elder care. Despite many studies concluding positive outcomes of Paro, we know that individuals react differently to Paro. It is a reasonable assumption that reactions will vary to similar technologies and those that will be developed and marketed in the future based on many internal and external factors (Golant, 2017). That is, personal histories and preferences toward different types of social robots and other new technologies will dictate their uptake or rejection (Abbott et al., 2019; Birks et al., 2016; Pu et al., 2020). Advance directives in end-of-life care have sought to ensure that the care provided to those who cannot decide for themselves is in accordance with their wishes (Dowling et al., 2020; Kossman, 2014; Mitchell, 2012; Poveda-Moral et al., 2021). There have naturally been challenges in the implementation of such decision-making in light of the complexity of dealing with terminal illnesses (de Boer et al., 2010; Emanuel, 1994; Kollisch et al., 2021). Nevertheless, making future choices in advance for using technologies is less dire. Emulating the core values associated with advanced care planning might be

significant in elder care planning of the future, where technologies are likely to be used more than it is now.

In our study, we found that carers would decide to use Paro for their older family member if there was a clear past preference for animals and/or toys. Similarly, Paro would not be used if there was clear nonpreference for animals. Thus, in both cases, they bring forth choices based on substituted judgment and thus respect the previous preferences of the older person. What is different from the above logic is that in a few cases, Paro will not be used because of past preference for animals since Paro is a robot raising concerns related to deception. Ultimately, the substituted judgment will have to balance the improvements in the well-being of the recreational capability against the likelihood of being stigmatized and infantilized.

We are aware that substituted and surrogate decision-making include challenging tasks (Cresp et al., 2020; Fetherstonhaugh et al., 2017; Kluge, 2008). We do not take the framework of future care planning as being absolute. What we want is to set up a default in which patients and their families have leverage in the clinical conversation. Another challenge is that advance directives may be intractable with regard to ongoing technological development. The geriatric care field, including long-term care environments for dementia patients, will increasingly utilize various advanced technologies that do not currently exist. So, individuals have to decide while they have intact cognitive abilities about an uncertain future. We propose a framework that enables caregivers—both family members and nursing professionals—and older adults to recognize and respond to the increasing integration of technologies into their care. It is prudent for end-users, families, and professional care networks to engage with existing technological options and plan for future requirements. Knowledge and prior planning would allow older persons to ensure that their future selves (when frail and unable to make a competent decision) are treated in the way they would have wanted and expected from their families and professional caregivers.

4.5 | Limitations

First, Paro is designed for use by those with cognitive diseases and disorders, explaining why several dozens of studies are available on its use with older persons with dementia. Readers may thus question whether asking cognitively healthy older individuals, their family carers, and professional carers would produce meaningful data. We certainly believe that it does. Recent empirical evidence pointing to the stigma associated with robotic use among older persons, for us, raises the important issue of how to “protect” oneself in the future when the use of robotic technologies among other new technologies is expected to increase. Second, as a qualitative exploration, the findings are not generalizable to other contexts, not only because of the limitation associated with the methodological approach (e.g., purposive sampling) used but more importantly, because participants' opinions on the social robot are contextualized within the society they live. Third, social desirability

is a further limitation where participants may have provided more positive information than they actually have about Paro. However, in light of the confidential nature of the project and the topic of discussion being not sensitive, we hope that the effect would be minimal. Fourth, participants were not given a Paro to experience before eliciting their responses. They were shown a picture. Although this is a clear limitation of the study design, Paro is an expensive technology (about USD 4500 and has been sold 5000 times since it came to the market, as per an ethnographic work; Wright, 2023). Its costs and rareness explain why, like our study, other studies have also used videos and photos instead of real-life interaction with technologies to elicit opinions (Coghlan et al., 2021; Fracasso et al., 2022; Kühne et al., 2022). Finally, we acknowledge that our framework of future care planning assumes that older persons would find themselves wanting and deciding in the same way when they have dementia. Choices and preferences are dynamic and prone to changes based on new experiences gained with time. Unfortunately, we did not include participants living with dementia in our current study.

5 | CONCLUSION

The use of animal-like social robots may continue to result in positive well-being, it, however, remains important to be aware of the prejudices associated with its use. Social norms and values play a significant role in shaping the use of new technologies and attributing prejudiced meanings to them. Technological development is advancing and its greater deployment is likely in the care of older persons. Though Paro is a “cute” and “harmless” social robot, there is a risk that future older persons with dementia may be seen as socially inferior when they use it or other similar technologies. Trivializing persons and their dignity should be taken into account when deciding for future selves, even if the person may or may not know that such trivializations are happening. It may thus be useful for those individuals who wish to protect themselves or their loved ones from possible technology-introduced prejudices, to ponder on making future care planning before they are in advanced old age possibly affected by cognitive decline. Moreover, the value of respect for persons should not make us shy away from playfulness just because people have grown older. Including *Homo Ludens* in our understanding of dignity holds potential to enrich our lives.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Tenzin Wangmo designed and supervised the project. Nadine Andrea Felber and Vanessa Duong conducted the interviews and transcribed the data. Yi Jiao (Angelina) Tian, Nadine Andrea Felber, Vanessa Duong, and Tenzin Wangmo carried out the first analysis for the paper. Tenzin Wangmo wrote the manuscript and finalized the data analysis for this manuscript. Emilian Mihailov contributed to the interpretation of the analyzed results and co-wrote the introduction and discussion. All authors have read and approved the version submitted. They take responsibility for the content of the paper.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The study would not have been possible without the kind time and experiences shared by the older persons, family caregivers, and professionals working in the context of elder care in Switzerland. We are indebted and we thank you. The authors acknowledge the support of the co-applicant of the funded project, Professor Delphine Roulet-Schwab, in the design of the overall project. The work of Emilian Mihailov was funded by the European Union (ERC, avataResponsibility, 101117761). This study is part of the "Smart Homes, Older Adults, And Caregivers: Facilitating Social Acceptance and Negotiating Responsibilities [RESOURCE] project," which is financed by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNF NRP-77 Digital Transformation, Grant Number 407740_187464/1). Open access funding provided by Universitat Basel.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Interview data relevant to this paper can be made available to the readers upon reasonable request made to the corresponding author. Furthermore, several of the interview participants have given consent to share their anonymized data on an Open Access Platform. This will be done at the end of the project in December 2024.

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How to cite this article: Wangmo, T., Duong, V., Felber, N. A., Tian, Y. J. (A), & Mihailov, E. (2024). No playing around with robots? Ambivalent attitudes toward the use of Paro in elder care. *Nursing Inquiry*, 31, e12645.

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